

Digital Sovereignty

Mohammed Saaida

Department of International Relations and Diplomacy, Faculty of Administration Sciences and Informatics, Al-Istiqlal University, Jericho – Palestine.

Email: confador@gmail.com

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7488-9832>

This work is a part of:		
	Science For All Publications	
	August 2023 Publications Vol: 6 Issue: 1 pp. 1-12	Electronic Self-publication Project References Number (SFAP 2400101/1)

Introductions:

Digital sovereignty, a concept that encompasses a state's independence in domestic and foreign policy within the digital sphere, has become a crucial aspect of statehood in the era of global digital transformation. It refers to the power and authority of a national government to make free decisions affecting citizens and businesses within the digital domain, and it is often seen as a measure of a state's stateness, security, and economic potential. The concept of digital sovereignty gained momentum due to the rapidly growing amounts of data, the challenging cyber security landscape, global political turmoil, and changes in international regulations. It is closely related to data sovereignty and sovereign cloud, which focus on the rules and reference architectures that can help safeguard data and ensure state control over technology and services in use.

This digital power grab isn't a sudden whim. It stems from the internet's paradoxical nature – a web with tangible infrastructure yet existing in the nebulous cyberspace. This raises the thorny question: how can laws forged in physical courts govern this borderless realm? Legal scholar Joel Reidenberg points out, networks themselves mimic sovereign states. Users "engage" through contracts, "rights" are defined by terms of service, and "police powers" manifest in operator sanctions. No wonder nations crave control over these virtual fiefdoms.

The implications of network sovereignty ripple beyond mere digital borders. It impacts national security, shaping how governments defend against cyber threats. It reshapes internet governance, raising questions about global connectivity and data flow. And most importantly, it affects the

user experience. Imagine navigating virtual checkpoints, with each border crossing potentially subjecting you to different rules and restrictions. This is the future digital sovereignty portends.

State Security in the Face of Network Challenges

Network sovereignty always faces reality. In the age of interconnected networks, traditional notions of state sovereignty face a formidable challenger: a porous digital landscape sculpted by star networks and private tunnels. As Allison Cavanagh argues in "Sociology in the Age of the Internet," this new architecture weakens state influence, a point echoed by Saskia Sassen and Joel R. Reidenberg. Sassen highlights the prevalence of private data conduits, especially in sensitive sectors like banking, demonstrating how these pathways erode the state's unified voice within cyberspace.

Situated amidst the dynamic interplay of Encryption and Fragmented Power lies an additional hurdle – encryption. Joel Reidenberg underscores the seamless migration of intellectual property across diverse networks, compelling businesses and creators to shroud their products in digital armor. This phenomenon precipitates a proliferation of encrypted content, intensifying the fracture of control within the state. In this intricate landscape, businesses, buoyed by influential lobby groups, not only navigate private tunnels but also contribute to the symphony of voices that intricately weaves through the complex dance of network governance.

Challenges in Internet Governance

From legislative skirmishes to national fortresses, the battle for internet control spans the globe. In the US, the fiery SOPA-PIPA debates ignited controversy over government attempts to curb online content. Across the Pacific, China's Great Firewall (Golden Shield Project) stands as a monument to digital censorship, meticulously filtering information within its borders. And in Russia, Roskomnadzor's growing powers amplify concerns about state surveillance in the online world. It is to say that global power play on the digital frontier

There is endless debate between calls for freedom and call for control. These diverse approaches expose the Gordian knot at the heart of internet governance: balancing freedom with control. Every policy and legislative intervention, from SOPA-PIPA's takedown notices to China's social media monitoring, sparks global debates about the appropriate boundaries of government influence in the online sphere. Can censorship be justified in the name of security? Does freedom of expression trump concerns about online harms? These are the questions that echo across borders, shaping the very future of the internet landscape.

These instances illuminate the multifaceted nature of challenges faced in governing the Internet. As nations grapple with the intricacies of balancing freedom and control in the digital realm, these initiatives spark debates on the global stage about the appropriate extent of governmental intervention in the online sphere.

SOPA-PIPA Legislation: Balancing Piracy Prevention and Net Neutrality Concerns

Recall the notorious SOPA and PIPA, the legislative siblings from the United States that embarked on a seemingly noble mission to vanquish online piracy, only to risk submerging the entire internet in the murky waters of censorship. Championed by Hollywood, these bills sought to empower law enforcement with the authority to blacklist websites, a formidable weapon against copyright infringers. However, the response was immediate and bipartisan. Legal luminaries such as Mark Lemley and David Levin sounded a resounding alarm with their rallying cry, "Don't Break the Internet," unleashing a tidal wave of public dissent. Is it a fumbled pursuit of pirates?

The shifting tides of protests and blackouts in the Face of Internet Blockades can not be unnoticed. As legislative blockades loomed, the internet unleashed its formidable arsenal of protests and blackouts. Wikipedia plunged into darkness, Senator Leahy, the staunch advocate of PIPA, found himself a target of public ire, and critics resonated with a unified outcry that both bills were nothing short of net neutrality's kryptonite. The underlying apprehension? The fear that attempting to block a handful of pirate websites could serve as a slippery slope towards widespread censorship, fundamentally altering the open expanse of the internet into a confined space controlled by both government and corporate entities.

SOPA and PIPA may be relics of the past, but their ghost still lingers. They serve as a stark reminder of the delicate dance between fighting piracy and protecting internet freedom. Every legislative step in the digital domain must be measured against this fragile balance. Can we curb infringement without compromising net neutrality? That's the question policymakers must constantly answer, ensuring that the internet remains a haven for innovation and expression, not a battleground for control.

The Golden Shield Project: Bridging the Divide Between Control and Access

Constructing the Reality of China's Digital Great Wall. Envision an internet divided, where the simple greeting of "Hello World" reaches you only in carefully curated whispers. This dystopian reality is embodied by the Golden Shield Project, more commonly known as China's infamous Great Firewall. A colossal digital barrier, it systematically blocks websites flagged as "problematic" by the government, rendering a significant portion of the internet off-limits for Chinese citizens. Scholar Min Jiang astutely captures the ensuing tension between netizens yearning for a free digital world and a government resolute in its determination to assert control over the online terrain.

Navigating the Digital Divide: Unveiling the Dynamics of the Golden Shield Project extends beyond the notion of a mere firewall—it's a dynamic battleground where state authority grapples with the aspirations of a connected populace. As the government erects digital borders, it asserts its power, igniting impassioned debates about information freedom and individual liberties.

Scholar Jiang expertly illuminates these nuanced tensions, revealing a continuous dialogue between those yearning for unfiltered access and a government steadfast in its mission to regulate the digital domain. How does one navigate the intricate web of interests and ideologies woven into the delicate balance of Control vs. Connection, and what implications does this dynamic interplay hold for the evolving landscape of digital governance and individual freedoms?

Roskomnadzor: Safeguarding Rights in the Digital Realm

The Federal Service for Supervision of Communications, Information Technology, and Mass Media, known as Roskomnadzor, is a Russian federal executive agency responsible for monitoring, controlling, and censoring Russian mass media. Established in 2008, Roskomnadzor oversees various aspects of media, including electronic media, mass communications, information technology, and telecommunications. It is also an authorized federal executive body for the protection of human subjects of personal data.

Roskomnadzor has faced sanctions from Canada, Ukraine, and the European Union due to its actions in restricting access to certain online platforms and services. The agency has been involved in controversies, such as attempting to block access to Telegram, which eventually led to the creation of government channels within the app. In 2020, Roskomnadzor officially gave up on trying to block Telegram, but continued to slow down access to Twitter for users in Russia. This decision was attributed to the platform's failure to remove content deemed illegal by Russian standards, and occasionally caused issues with major commercial services and access to websites with domain names ending in ".t.co".

Russia has significantly expanded laws and regulations to tighten control over internet infrastructure, online content, and the privacy of communications. The Sovereign Internet Law, signed by President Vladimir Putin in May 2019, aims to protect the Russian segment of the internet from threats to its security integrity and sustainability, but in reality, it further expands the state's control over internet infrastructure. This law, along with other state legislations, has impeded the freedom of expression and access to information in Russia.

The right to privacy is one of the most important aspects of digital governance, and it has been the subject of intense public interest and debate in national security surveillance. Balancing privacy and security in the digital age is not a zero-sum game, and finding the right equilibrium is crucial for making informed judgments about how to strike the balance between privacy and security. As digital network technology continues to advance, it is essential to understand the impact of these technologies on both privacy and security to find a real equilibrium and identify technological and legal approaches that may enhance both security and privacy.

This intersection of legislation and the assertion of network sovereignty underscores the ongoing global discourse surrounding digital governance, individual rights, and state control in an

increasingly interconnected world. The nuanced balance between privacy protection and the free exchange of information remains a critical consideration in shaping the regulatory landscape.

Global Perspectives on Internet Control

The tactics employed by China in regulating the internet could serve as a precedent for numerous countries globally. An illustrative case is the internet censorship witnessed during the Arab Spring, where the Egyptian government, in particular, sought to curtail access to Facebook and Twitter. Similarly, in the context of the 2011 England riots, the British government endeavored to restrict access to Blackberry Messenger. These instances underscore a broader trend wherein governments grapple with the challenges posed by digital communication platforms during periods of social upheaval. The strategic use of internet censorship as a tool for maintaining control and mitigating potential threats reflects a recurring theme in the evolving landscape of global governance. The actions of diverse governments in regulating online communication platforms highlight the delicate balance between the preservation of public order and the protection of individual freedoms, a balance that is subject to ongoing scrutiny and debate in the realm of digital governance.

Global internet regulations vary significantly among nations, with some countries allowing essentially unrestricted access, while others have strict laws that hold sites accountable for content and publication of personal information. A 2011 study from INSEAD and the Oxford Internet Institute found that 42% of respondents supported government regulation, 26% disagreed, and 28% neither agreed nor disagreed. Approximately 59% of all respondents thought that government should censor online content to protect public order.

The internet has become one of the most important means of communication, enabling people to access information, communicate with others, and engage in various activities. As a result, governments must navigate the challenges posed by digital communication platforms during periods of social upheaval. The strategic use of internet censorship as a tool for maintaining control and mitigating potential threats reflects a recurring theme in the evolving landscape of global governance. The actions of diverse governments in regulating online communication platforms highlight the delicate balance between the preservation of public order and the protection of individual freedoms, a balance that is subject to ongoing scrutiny and debate in the realm of digital governance.

Perspectives on Internet Governance: Navigating Boundaries and Control

Within the discourse on internet governance, a prevailing sentiment exists that questions the legitimacy of government intervention in the digital realm. Law Professor David Post from the University of Georgetown contends that applying statehood concepts to a domain inherently devoid of physical boundaries, like the internet, poses a formidable challenge. He emphasizes the

complexity arising when 150 jurisdictions concurrently enforce their laws, characterizing it as a conflict-of-law nightmare.

Proponents of an open internet, including figures like John Perry Barlow, argue that the current state of the internet is inherently resistant to traditional governance and should maintain its openness. Barlow's influential essay, written during the 1990s, remains pertinent in contemporary debates despite the considerable evolution of the internet. In his work, "A Declaration of the Independence of Cyberspace," Barlow vehemently advocates for governmental abstention from internet affairs.

The concept of Network Sovereignty, as explored in the context of internet governance, reverberates across dimensions of state security, law enforcement in the digital sphere, and the individual's utilization of the internet. The ongoing efforts of private citizens to circumvent governmental restrictions and legal mechanisms on the internet, often employing tools like VPNs, underscore the persistent tension between individual freedoms and governmental oversight in the digital age. This complex interplay shapes the trajectory of internet governance, prompting critical considerations regarding the balance between security, individual liberties, and the evolving nature of the online landscape.

Internet governance is a novel field that enables observations to be made on the power dynamics between states and transnational companies, as well as the role of international institutions in shaping norms impacting the internet. The struggle to shape the norms impacting such a key technological resource highlights tensions between states and transnational companies, and the ongoing evolution of internet governance serves as a field of institutional experimentation.

In conclusion, the discourse on internet governance is marked by diverse perspectives and challenges, as stakeholders grapple with the complexities of governing a domain that transcends traditional boundaries and legal frameworks. The ongoing evolution of the internet and the increasing influence of non-state actors, such as private citizens and transnational companies, further complicate the landscape of internet governance, emphasizing the need for a comprehensive and collaborative approach to navigating the boundaries and controls in this ever-changing digital landscape.

The Role and Implications of Virtual Private Networks (VPNs)

Virtual Private Networks (VPNs) play a crucial role in navigating the challenges posed by network sovereignty and governmental restrictions on internet access. VPNs enable a computer to reroute its internet connection from one location to another, concealing the actual point of origin and making it appear as if the user is accessing the internet from a different location. This technology is essential for accessing content that is otherwise restricted in countries like China.

The prevalence and functionality of VPNs raise complex questions surrounding digital privacy, security, and the global flow of information. VPNs serve as a tool for circumventing restrictions and a potential subject of surveillance, exemplifying the intricate landscape of digital governance. The dual nature of VPNs highlights the challenges of balancing individual freedoms and state control in the online sphere.

The prevalence and functionality of VPNs raise intricate questions surrounding digital privacy, security, and the global flow of information. The dual nature of VPNs as a tool for circumventing restrictions and a potential subject of surveillance exemplifies the complex landscape of digital governance, where technological innovations intersect with regulatory challenges, prompting ongoing discussions on the balance between individual freedoms and state control in the online sphere.

Copyright Protection and Network Sovereignty

The pursuit of network sovereignty by governments is often motivated by the imperative to safeguard copyright within their borders. The rationale behind initiatives like SOPA-PIPA lies in the prevention of what is perceived as a form of theft, a proactive measure to preserve intellectual property. Content providers, driven by the desire to ensure their creative works are utilized as intended, invoke the principles of property rights associated with their content. This imperative extends into various domains, notably exemplified in the realm of e-commerce.

Within the context of copyright protection, SOPA-PIPA represents a legislative effort to grapple with the challenges posed by digital infringement. The contention revolves around striking a balance between enabling the free flow of information and preserving the rights of content creators. The inherent tension in achieving this equilibrium underscores the broader debates in intellectual property law, as governments navigate the intricacies of digital governance and the evolving landscape of creative expression in the online sphere.

Network sovereignty has implications for state security, Internet governance, and the users of the Internet's national and international networks. Governments may want to enact network sovereignty to protect copyright within their borders and ensure the protection of their citizens' privacy. Network sovereignty can be viewed as a form of control, often in the form of law enforcement over such boundaries.

Global standards for copyright and encryption are viewed as one way that governments could cooperate to regulate e-commerce and protect network sovereignty. However, it is possible that governments may not be able to keep up with regulating these initiatives, as seen in the 1995 Clipper Chip system, where the Clinton administration in the United States reneged on its original policy.

One of the most effective ways to regulate e-commerce is to allow Internet Service Providers (ISPs) to implement measures to protect copyright and intellectual property rights. The World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) has also been involved in discussions and negotiations to strengthen the communication of copyright information, study new issues of copyright protection, and constantly improve the level of copyright protection.

In conclusion, the pursuit of network sovereignty by governments is a complex issue that involves balancing the need for copyright protection with the challenges posed by digital infringement and the evolving landscape of creative expression in the online sphere. Governments must navigate the intricacies of digital governance and cooperate with other nations to establish effective regulations and protect the rights of content creators.

E-Commerce Dynamics: Balancing Property Rights and Open Values

In the current landscape, legal actions between private networks highlight the importance of assertive property rights protection in e-commerce. The smooth operation of e-commerce on the Internet relies on merchants' ability to impose access restrictions and encryption, which not only safeguards their content but also protects the information of those engaging in content transactions. A common approach to regulate e-commerce effectively is to delegate market oversight to Internet service providers (ISPs).

However, there is a counterargument against using network sovereignty for e-commerce regulation, as it could compromise the Internet's foundational principles of egalitarianism and openness. This perspective argues that introducing regulatory measures would extend beyond managing the content itself, encompassing the very manner in which content is consumed. The tension between the need to protect property rights and the commitment to preserving the open nature of the Internet fuels critical discussions on the future trajectory of e-commerce governance. Striking a delicate balance becomes crucial, as the evolving landscape of digital commerce prompts a reevaluation of regulatory frameworks and their implications on individual freedoms and online accessibility.

WIPO's Role in Intellectual Property Protection and Global Governance

The World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) is a global forum for intellectual property policy, information, and cooperation, with a mission to lead the development of a balanced and effective international intellectual property system that promotes innovation and creativity for a better and more sustainable future. WIPO provides tailored assistance to developing and least developed countries (LDCs) to help them develop national intellectual property strategies that align with their cultural and economic development goals and priorities. These strategies aim to enhance a country's ability to create, protect, and disseminate economically valuable intellectual property assets, fostering an enabling environment to harness innovative and creative potential.

WIPO's national intellectual property strategies are cross-cutting, as they link intellectual property with a wide range of public policy areas to enhance coherence and coordination. The organization offers policy advice, data and analysis, best practices, and other customized guidance to support the needs and priorities of its member states. WIPO's work is overseen and evaluated by external and internal bodies, and the organization is committed to improving sustainability within its operations and activities.

In the context of artificial intelligence (AI) and intellectual property, WIPO provides a multi-stakeholder forum to advance the understanding of the intellectual property issues involved in the production and distribution of economic and cultural goods and services. The organization is tasked with addressing the fundamental questions that arise from the emergence of AI, such as whether AI innovation and creation need intellectual property incentives and if changes to the existing intellectual property frameworks are necessary.

China's Cyber Sovereignty: A Complex Landscape of Control

China's concept of cyber sovereignty, has become a cornerstone of the country's Internet policy and is seamlessly integrated into its foreign policy agenda. Despite its prominence, the precise definition of cyber sovereignty remains somewhat nebulous within Chinese discourse. The Great Firewall, a combination of legislative measures and technologies enforced by the People's Republic of China, stands as a robust tool for domestic Internet regulation, achieving internet censorship by blocking access to designated foreign websites and deliberately slowing down cross-border internet traffic.

China's cyber sovereignty efforts have both a domestic and an international component, and they will result in an internet that will be less open and more controlled. The Chinese government and the ruling Communist Party assert cyber sovereignty, asserting control over all digital resources within China, spanning servers, user data, technical infrastructure, and tech firms operating both domestically and internationally.

China's legislative landscape reinforces this narrative. The 2017 Cybersecurity Law mandates that firms providing "critical information infrastructure" in mainland China store their data on government-run servers, exemplified by the state's access to resources like Apple's China-based iCloud data. The more recent Data Security Law of 2021 further empowers the Chinese government to conduct national security audits on firms operating in China that amass user data. This intricate web of regulations reflects the evolving nature of cyber sovereignty and its implications for state control, corporate compliance, and the broader landscape of digital governance in China.

France's Project Andromède and the Sovereign Cloud Initiative

In 2009, France embarked on Project Andromède, a significant venture allocating €285 million towards the development of a "cloud souverain" or sovereign cloud. The government's substantial investment, amounting to €75 million for each of its two national champions, Cloudwatt and Numergy, aimed to establish a robust national cloud infrastructure. However, the practical outcomes fell short of expectations, as the combined services provided by both entities amounted to a mere €8 million in value.

The trajectory of Project Andromède took a notable turn on January 1, 2020, with the termination of all services. Clients were then informed that their data had been deleted. This turn of events prompts critical reflection on the efficacy of large-scale government initiatives in the realm of technology and data management. The stark disparity between investment and realized services raises questions about the feasibility and strategic planning underlying such ambitious projects. The case of Project Andromède serves as a cautionary tale in navigating the complexities of national digital infrastructure initiatives and the challenges of achieving intended outcomes in the rapidly evolving landscape of cloud technology.

Germany's Pursuit of Digital Sovereignty: The openDesk Initiative

The openDesk project, led by the German Federal Ministry of the Interior (BMI) in collaboration with Dataport, Univention, OpenXchange, Nextcloud, XWiki, and OpenProject, aims to revolutionize digital technology in public administration by creating a 100% open-source, secure, decentralized, and privacy-respecting environment for the German public administration. The project, previously known as the Sovereign Workplace, is set to have a lasting impact on how governments approach digital technology and is part of the German government's broader strategy to strengthen digital sovereignty.

Crucially, openDesk engages in a strategic collaboration with a team of open-source specialists, drawing expertise from prominent entities such as Collabora, Nextcloud, OpenProject, OpenXchange, Univention, XWiki, and others. This collaboration underscores the commitment to leveraging the collective knowledge of open-source communities to shape the development of administrative workspaces tailored to meet the unique challenges and opportunities posed by the digital age.

As nations grapple with the complexities of digital governance, initiatives like openDesk exemplify a proactive approach to cultivating digital sovereignty. By fostering collaboration with leading open-source specialists, Germany positions itself at the forefront of innovative solutions, acknowledging the importance of community-driven approaches in shaping the future of administrative workspaces and, by extension, the broader landscape of digital governance.

Russia's Sovereign Internet Law: Navigating Digital Boundaries

Enacted in 2019, the Sovereign Internet Law comprises a set of amendments to existing Russian legislation. This legislative framework introduces mandates for Internet surveillance and endows the Russian government with unprecedented powers to partition Russia from the global Internet. An integral facet of this initiative involves the creation of a national fork of the Domain Name System (DNS), a move with profound implications for the autonomy and control exerted over digital communication within the country.

The Sovereign Internet Law exemplifies a deliberate effort by the Russian government to assert greater authority in the digital realm. By enhancing surveillance capabilities and introducing measures to insulate Russia from the global Internet, the legislation reflects a strategic approach to both national security and the preservation of information sovereignty. However, this move prompts critical considerations regarding the potential consequences for freedom of information, digital rights, and the broader landscape of global digital governance. The intricate interplay between state control and the open nature of the Internet underscores the ongoing challenges in reconciling national interests with the principles of an interconnected digital world.

Digital Sovereignty Initiatives in Arab Countries

In recent years, Arab countries have embarked on strategic initiatives to assert control and autonomy in the digital realm, emphasizing the pursuit of digital sovereignty. The motivations behind these endeavors are rooted in the desire to safeguard national interests, protect cultural values, and navigate the evolving challenges posed by the interconnected nature of the global digital landscape.

Various Arab countries have implemented measures to regulate and govern the use of the internet within their borders. These initiatives encompass a range of strategies, including the development of legislative frameworks, the establishment of regulatory bodies, and the implementation of technological solutions to monitor and control digital activities.

One notable example is the Internet censorship witnessed during the Arab Spring, where several governments, such as Egypt, attempted to restrict access to social media platforms like Facebook and Twitter. These actions reflect the complexities of managing digital spaces during periods of social and political upheaval.

The multifaceted nature of digital sovereignty initiatives in Arab countries prompts critical reflections on the delicate balance between preserving national interests and ensuring an open, interconnected digital environment. As these nations navigate the complexities of digital governance, the ongoing discourse on the implications for individual freedoms, information access, and the global nature of the internet remains central to shaping the future of digital sovereignty in the Arab world.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the global landscape of internet control is evolving through challenges to state influence. Private companies create independent data pathways and encrypt information, reducing state control. Diverse approaches to internet regulation worldwide spark debates on freedom versus control.

Policymakers face a delicate dance, balancing freedom of expression with content regulation and national security. Case studies like SOPA-PIPA and China's Golden Shield Project illustrate the complexity of this balance. Shifting public discourse and protests shape internet governance, influencing legislative decisions.

Governments globally use internet censorship during social unrest, raising concerns about balancing security and individual freedoms. Varying approaches to internet regulation reflect ongoing debates on government intervention. Network sovereignty, individual circumvention efforts, and tensions between states and companies complicate governance, requiring collaboration.

Virtual Private Networks (VPNs) are crucial for accessing restricted content, prompting questions on digital privacy and security. The pursuit of network sovereignty involves balancing copyright protection with challenges posed by digital infringement.

In e-commerce, a balance between property rights and open values is evident. The World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) aids developing countries in formulating intellectual property strategies. China's cyber sovereignty concept is integral to its internet policy, while details about France's Project An remain unclear.